

4B_1c Central FDP

- Introduction
- Pros / Cons
- Using the central FAIR Data Point
 - Editing existing data
 - Rights to edit metadata
 - Common issues
- Next steps

Introduction

If you're unable to implement any of the previously suggested methods to set up your own FAIR Data Point, you have the option to utilize the [central FDP](#) managed by Health-RI directly.

With this option, your metadata source is not automatically linked to the FDP, so if possible, we recommend setting up your own FDP.

Pros / Cons

Pro

- Dataset owner doesn't need to setup and maintain the FAIR Data Point to add metadata to the National Health Data Catalogue

Con

- The central FDP supports one metadata schema at the moment.
- Metadata needs to be maintained and updated manually.

Using the central FAIR Data Point

1. In order to use the central FDP you will need an account login. For this please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl . A Health-RI colleague will then check if use of central FDP in your case is the right solution.

If the use of a central FDP is approved, you will receive your login information.

2. Go to <https://fdp-acc.healthdata.nl/> and login
3. Navigate to "Catalogs" and click on +Create.
 - a. Fill in your metadata.
 - b. **Note that non-used properties recommended with mandatory sub-properties need to be actively removed by clicking X next to the property**

- i The highest level of a resource that is added to the FDP is called a “catalog” (e.g. a project) which can contain one or more datasets (see below).

FAIR Data point set up:

4. Click on **Save**. You will be taken to a new catalog page

⚠ The saving process can take up to a minute

5. To create a dataset click on **+Create** button. A new page will open where you can enter your metadata.

- a. **Note that non-used properties recommended with mandatory sub-properties need to be actively removed by clicking X next to the property**

6. After filling your metadata click on **Save** on the bottom of the page. You will then be redirected to the dataset page.

⚠ You need to fill all mandatory fields to be able to save the dataset

7. To publish the dataset click on **“Publish”** on the top right of the page. A dialog will pop up requiring to confirm the action.

⚠ The saving process can take up to a minute

- i If not using a variable with mandatory subvariables the variable needs to be manually removed.

8. To create a distribution of your dataset click on **+Create** in the top right corner. You can then fill out your metadata in the form.

- a. **Note that non-used properties recommended with mandatory sub-properties need to be actively removed by clicking X next to the property**

9. After filling your metadata click on **Save** on the bottom of the page. You will then be redirected to the distribution page.

Saving process can take up to a minute

i If not using a variable with mandatory subvariables the variable needs to be manually removed.

10. To publish the distribution click on **“Publish”** on the top right of the page. A dialog will pop up requiring to confirm the action.
11. You can repeat this process for multiple datasets and/or multiple distributions.
12. After entering your data, please check that the data is appears as expected in the central FDP.
13. If data appear correctly, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl to begin [5. Metadata har vesting](#).

Editing existing data

1. Login into the FDP at <https://fdp-acc.healthdata.nl/>
2. In the search bar search for your **Catalog** or **Dataset** (or other metadata class you wish to edit)
3. Select you metadata.
4. Click **Edit**.
5. Edit and save.

Rights to edit medata

Editing of metadata can be only done if you have the correct rights. Initially the person who created the metadata is the owner of the Catalog or Dataset and the only one who can edit them. To provide more individuals with editing rights:

1. Login into the FDP at <https://fdp-acc.healthdata.nl/>
2. In the search bar search for your **Catalog** or **Dataset** (or other metadata class you wish others to edit)
3. Click on **Settings**
4. In **Invite users** search for the user you wish to have access and editing rights. Select either Owner or Data provider. Owner can both edit and give rights to other users. Data providers can only edit.
5. Click **+Invite**

i The rights to edit are assigned directly per class, this means that rights to edit a Catalog do not provide editing rights for all Datasets in said catalog and need to be provided seprately.

Common issues

∨ I lost my password

To reset your password, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl with the registered email

∨ I entered a field wrong, how can I change it.

On the catalog layer only admin can change the submitted metadata. If you need to change a field in Catalog, contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

For Datasets and Distributions you can find the edit option on the top right corner of the respective layer. If you have trouble finding your catalog, use the advanced search.

∨ Unable to update entity data.

One or more of the fields have been submitted in the wrong format. Please make sure to check variable's format in the model [GitHub - Health-RI/health-ri-metadata at master](#)

Often, regards the **contact point email** which needs to be in vcard as <mailto:NAME@DOMAIN.nl> and cannot be submitted as NAME@DOMAIN.nl.

All **links** are required in IRI format, if your link includes characters not in ASCII it will also not be saved. Similarly links need to include the transfer protocol (ie. https://)

All time indicators (issued, modified) also need to follow the correct time format. Please check by selecting the a date on via the calendar rather than typing.

If you are unsure where the issue lies, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

∨ Unable to load (Dashboard/Catalog/Dataset)

If an update of the entity has been recently done, refreshing the page usually solves the issue.

If you are unsure where the issue lies, please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

∨ Other issues

please contact servicedesk@health-ri.nl

✔ Next steps

If you have an FDP and compliant metadata ([4A Metadata mapping](#)) within your FDP, the data can be harvested by the National Catalogue. For this step see [5. Metadata harvesting](#) .

